

Studies on Metal Chelates of 5-Iodo-8-Hydroxyquinolino-4-(*p*-Tolyl)sulphonamide and 5-Iodo-7-Chloro-8-Hydroxyquinolino-4-(*p*-Tolyl)sulphonamide as Potential Drugs

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Metal chelates of 5-iodo-8-hydroxyquinolino-4-(*p*-tolyl)sulphonamide [IHQTS] and 5-iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinolino-4-(*p*-tolyl)sulphonamide [ICHQTS] with metals like Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses and ir spectra. They were screened for their antibacterial activity against gram positive bacteria *S. aureus* and gram negative *E. coli* to test the change in antibacterial activity of ligands on complexation.

THE chemistry of quinoline and *p*-toluene sulphonamide have attracted special attention because of their therapeutic properties¹⁻³. Some of the sulphonamides were used as drugs for diseases like cancer⁴, tuberculosis⁴, diabetes⁵, malaria⁶, leprosy⁷ and convulsion⁸. They were found to be active against different types of bacteria. It has been observed recently that some drugs have increased activity when administered as metal complexes, more so their metal chelates⁹⁻¹⁰. A similar indication was also found in our previous study¹¹. In continuation of our previous work and to test the change in antibacterial activity of ligands on chelation, we report here the synthesis of metal chelates of IHQTS and ICHQTS with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and recrystallized. The metal-ligand ratio was determined by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation, which showed 1 : 2 complexation. Infrared spectra were recorded on an automatic Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in KBr phase. Metals were estimated by standard methods¹², sulphur by modified Messenger's method¹³ and nitrogen by modified Kjeldahl's procedure¹⁴.

Ligands: The ligands IHQTS and ICHQTS were prepared by the action of chlorosulphonic acid on 5-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline and 5-iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, thus getting their sulphonyl chlorides. These sulphonyl chlorides were then allowed to react with *p*-toluidine in ethanolic medium. This resulted in the formation of precipitates of IHQTS and ICHQTS respectively. The precipitates were filtered, washed well with ethanol and recrystallized.

Complexes: IHQTS and ICHQTS were dissolved in warm distilled water and treated with

an appropriate amount of metal salt solution in distilled water at a pH ranging from 8-9. The pH was maintained by using a solution of 8.50 ml to 21.30 ml of 0.1 N NaOH and 50 ml of 0.1 M H₂BO₃. The resulting precipitates of the complexes were filtered, washed well with hot distilled water and dried in an oven at 110-120°.

Infrared spectra: A broad distinct band at 2950 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of IHQTS and another at 3100 cm⁻¹ in ICHQTS were found. These values are less than the prescribed limit (3700-3300 cm⁻¹) for -OH group. It is due to hydrogen bonding¹⁵⁻¹⁶. On this basis the intramolecular hydrogen bonded chelate structures (-O-H...N-) have been proposed for the ligands. A critical examination of the spectra of metal chelates indicates that the bands at 2950 cm⁻¹ and 3100 cm⁻¹ present in the ligands shift to higher values (3600-3300 cm⁻¹) in the chelates. Thus on metal chelate formation, the bands between 3600-3300 cm⁻¹ which appear in all chelates are not present in the original ligands^{17,18}. The disappearance of H-bonded -OH in the ligands and its reappearance in the metal chelates are suggestive of O-M-N bond formation, where M is a metal atom. The bands of medium intensity around 1600 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of ligands due to ν(>C=N-) shift to lower values with weak intensity in the spectra of chelates. It is due to M←N bond formation. The bands between 1600-1490 cm⁻¹ are due to aromatic rings. The sharp bands around 500 cm⁻¹ and 800 cm⁻¹

are due to $\begin{array}{c} | \\ -C-I \\ | \end{array}$ and $\begin{array}{c} | \\ -C-Cl \\ | \end{array}$ respectively¹⁹. The presence of sulphonamide group has been established by a characteristic band in the vicinity of the region 1370 cm⁻¹^{20,21}.

Results and Discussion

The results of analyses and colour of the chelates are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	%N Found (Calcd.)	%S Found (Calcd.)	%M Found (Calcd.)	%I Found (Calcd.)	%Cl Found (Calcd.)
Fe-IHQTS	Brown	6.00 (5.99)	6.89 (6.85)	5.97 (5.98)	27.16 (27.19)	
Co-IHQTS	Light blue	5.98 (5.97)	6.85 (6.83)	6.30 (6.29)	27.08 (27.10)	
Ni-IHQTS	Green	5.91 (5.97)	6.80 (6.83)	6.30 (6.26)	27.10 (27.11)	
Cu-IHQTS	Light blue	5.90 (5.94)	6.81 (6.79)	6.71 (6.74)	26.91 (26.97)	
Cd-IHQTS	White	5.64 (5.65)	6.47 (6.46)	11.38 (11.34)	25.62 (25.64)	
Pb-IHQTS	Yellow	5.16 (5.16)	5.92 (5.89)	19.11 (19.09)	23.41 (23.40)	
Fe-ICHQTS	Light brown	5.56 (5.58)	6.42 (6.38)	5.56 (5.57)	25.31 (25.32)	7.01 (7.07)
Co-ICHQTS	Blue	5.57 (5.56)	6.43 (6.36)	5.85 (5.86)	25.27 (25.24)	7.10 (7.05)
Ni-ICHQTS	Light green	5.55 (5.56)	6.37 (6.36)	5.85 (5.83)	25.26 (25.25)	7.06 (7.05)
Cu-ICHQTS	Blue	5.58 (5.54)	6.32 (6.33)	6.29 (6.28)	25.10 (25.13)	7.00 (7.02)
Cd-ICHQTS	White	5.30 (5.28)	6.07 (6.04)	10.65 (10.60)	23.94 (23.97)	6.64 (6.70)
Pb-ICHQTS	Light yellow	4.87 (4.85)	5.57 (5.54)	17.99 (17.95)	21.96 (22.00)	6.10 (6.15)

The overall study and the analytical data given in Table 1 show that both the ligands form chelates of the type ML_2 where L = ligand. Hence a composition of the type $M(C_{16}H_{11}SN_2O_3I)_2$ and $M(C_{16}H_{11}SN_2O_3Cl)_2$ may be given for the metal chelates of IHQTS and ICHQTS respectively.

The reaction for IHQTS may be written as in Fig. 1. A similar reaction can be written for

ICHQTS also. The structure of the metal chelate is in good agreement with past workers^{22,23}.

The exact melting points could not be determined but were more than 300°.

Screening for antibacterial activity : The bacteriostatic properties of ligands and their metal chelates were studied by the usual cup-plate agar diffusion technique²⁴ against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. 1.0% (w/v) solutions^{25,26} of the compounds were prepared. A mixture of equal volumes of isopropyl alcohol and dioxan was taken and its 20% solution was used as solvent. Four holes (about 5 mm diam) were cut in the agar medium enriched with culture and 0.1 ml of 1.0% solution of the compounds were put in these holes. The petridishes were allowed to remain in the refrigerator at 4-8° for about 1 hr to allow the diffusion of the solutions. These petridishes were then transferred to an incubator maintained at 37° and the zones of inhibition were noted

after 24 hr of incubation by measuring with callipers. The control with solvent under identical conditions showed no activity. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. Compound No.	Zone of inhibition in mm		Sl. Compound No.	Zone of inhibition in mm	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1. IHQTS	10	—	8. ICHQTS	15	15
2. Fe-IHQTS	24	24	9. Fe-ICHQTS	26	27
3. Co-IHQTS	—	21	10. Co-ICHQTS	29	—
4. Ni-IHQTS	23	23	11. Ni-ICHQTS	21	21
5. Cu-IHQTS	25	24	12. Cu-ICHQTS	26	25
6. Cd-IHQTS	20	—	13. Cd-ICHQTS	—	—
7. Pb-IHQTS	22	—	14. Pb-ICHQTS	24	24

Compound No. 1 showed a little activity towards *S. aureus* and no activity towards *E. coli*, while compound No. 8 showed activity against both the organisms. Compound No. 3 showed no activity against *S. aureus* while compounds No. 6, 7 and 10 showed no activity against *E. coli* but were active against *S. aureus*. Compound No. 13 showed no activity against both the organisms. We can thus, in general say that antibacterial activity is enhanced on complexation of IHQTS and ICHQTS with metals.

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